

WAYS OF DEVELOPING THE METHODOLOGY OF THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE AS A NON-NATIVE: PROBLEMS AND TRENDS.

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Annotation. This article deals with the problems of teaching Russian as a foreign language and as a non-native. The patterns of understanding and development of this branch of linguodidactics are revealed.

Keywords: Russian as a foreign language, general didactic principles, methodological principles, RCN (Russian as a non-native language), RCT (Russian as a foreign language), general didactic principles, speech skills, skills, linguistic justification.

Russian – the language of interethnic and international communication puts forward the tasks of an increasingly thorough and informed understanding of the laws of the development of such a branch of linguodidactics as “the methodology of teaching Russian as a non-native language.”

Russian Russian as a non-native language is divided into the methodology of the Russian language as a foreign language (RKI) and the methodology of the Russian language in the national school (RANS).

There are many similarities between these two branches of linguodidactics, and therefore we can talk about the unity of the basic provisions and principles of the methodology of the Russian language as a non-native as a whole. Specific methodological principles for the methodology of the Russian language as a non-native, distinguishing it from other branches of linguodidactics, are :

- the principle of communicative orientation of training;
- the principle of comprehensive training in various aspects of speech activity and various aspects of language;
- the principle of unity and interrelation between the processes of acquiring knowledge and skills and the process of automating skills;
- the principle of correlation with the native language of students.

As a branch of linguodidactics, the RCN methodology implements the general didactic principles of unity of teaching and upbringing, consciousness, activity, visibility, etc..

Russian as a native language and the methodology of the Russian language as a non-native language have significant differences in terms of the implementation of general didactic provisions and the definition of teaching principles.

It is not quite enough to consider methodology as the science of what to teach and how to teach. It is also necessary to determine who to teach, for what purpose and in what conditions. Although the question is who to teach? – it has already been set in the methodology, however, further development of this problem seems relevant.

The goals of teaching Russian to non-Russians are specific. This includes not only mastering a certain range of knowledge about the language, but also acquiring skills and abilities that determine speech activity in Russian.

In educational institutions with the Russian language of instruction, the object of study is the language itself, which the student already knows to some extent and which he uses when studying all other subjects, and at the same time "the school is obliged to develop and improve the previously established speech skills of students, to achieve awareness of what they have already learned spontaneously, by imitations".

For the methodology of teaching Russian as a non-native language, the tasks and content of teaching are different. Therefore, there is a rethinking of a number of general didactic principles, a reassessment of their role in the educational process.

If the purpose of teaching non-Russians is defined as the formation of speech skills in Russian, then this general formulation of the goal is the same for all levels of education.

As you know, the forms of speech activity are different : These are oral and written, monologue and dialogic speech, etc. The spheres of communication in which the language functions and in which students should use it are also different. The level of speech proficiency planned for a certain contingent of trainees at each stage of training is also different.

But if the purpose of teaching, for example, at the initial stage in secondary school is to master secondary speech skills (mainly oral) in the field of everyday communication, then teaching methods and techniques implemented at this stage in schools with Uzbek or another language of instruction can be combined.

As for the age characteristics of the trainees, the goals and methods of teaching Russian in any school with a non-Russian language of instruction are closer to each other than the goals and methods of teaching at a university. The difference lies, in particular, in the fact that students need to learn how to record lectures on the specialty, for which they must master the language of the specialty, the ability to record oral speech in writing.

Russian Russian is the second, third, etc., if the age of the students coincides, then there is a need to take into account factors such as the presence or absence of a language environment, typological features of the Russian language in comparison with the native language of the students, whether the Russian language is the second, third, etc. for this contingent of students, what is the motivation for learning Russian (natural or artificially created, educational or extracurricular etc.).

Let's consider the ways of applying some general didactic principles, taking into account their specificity and contrast in the methodology of teaching other subjects (including the native language) in order to find out the degree of their reinterpretation when teaching a non-native language.

Russian Russian Russian Russian The analysis of the juxtaposition of general didactic principles in the methodology of the RCT and the methodology of the Russian language as a native language emphasizes the independence of these branches of linguodidactics and does not exclude that the methodology of the Russian language in the Russian school and the methodology of the Russian language in the national school mutually enrich each other and that the methodology of the RCN, adopting all the best from the experience of the Russian methodology, strengthened under its direct influence. influence and with her help.

In didactics, one of the most important principles of teaching is the principle of developing learning (or the development of the student's comprehending ability).

In the modern theory of cognition, thinking is understood as comprehending mental activity. This is seen as the basis for creating a scientifically sound (pedagogically and psychologically) concept of the development and implementation of thinking in the process of teaching specific disciplines.

The most important for the formation of comprehending thinking in pedagogy is recognized as such a way of cognition, which carries out "the evidential deduction of one position on the basis of others, from which it necessarily follows."

When a student of a school with a non-Russian language of instruction receives in advance in a ready-made form the necessary knowledge to build language models, the process of assimilation of actions associated with the generation of independent statements at the time of the need for a particular speech action is inhibited. The reason is that a certain sequence of actions turns out to be unprocessed. This provision is equally characteristic of teaching the Russian language to both foreigners and students and students of national educational institutions.

If the trainee, gradually performing the necessary actions, is forced to independently come to receive a speech unit, then the process of forming the necessary mental actions in the right speech situation begins to function during the acquisition of new information and is much faster and more firmly fixed in the process of exercises.

The scientific principle has long been developed and widely implemented in didactics.

When implementing the scientific principle, the difference in understanding it when teaching native and non-native languages is especially clearly manifested. The application of the principle of scientific approach in teaching Russian as a native language presupposes the communication of only such information about the language that is firmly established in modern linguistic science, the coverage of these phenomena in their interrelation and development.

When teaching non-Russian students, the main thing is not the communication of information about the language, but the formation of speech skills and abilities. The whole learning process is based on strictly verified scientific data not only of linguistics, but also of psychology, psycholinguistics and methodology.

The language material introduced into the speech of students is located in a methodically thought-out and scientifically based system, which, as a rule, does not coincide with the traditional system of arrangement and study of language categories in scientific (including school) grammar. However, the absence of a traditional arrangement of language material in programs and textbooks for non-Russian students cannot be regarded as a denial of scientific and systematic, if there is a system of dissemination of the model, a system of expressed relations, etc. The main thing is that the training should not be based on randomly collected material and that all the information provided to the learners should correspond to the current level of development of the Russian language.

The principle of consciousness in the methodology of teaching a non-native language should be understood not as a requirement of conscious assimilation of knowledge about the language, but as the need for awareness of speech actions in the learning process, followed by their automation and the use of acquired skills in active speech activity.

Today there is no unambiguous understanding of the relationship between conscious and unconscious in the possession of speech in general and speech in a non-native language in particular. In the process of mastering speech, the components consciously directed and controlled by consciousness have a fairly high specific gravity. To learn how to manage their optimal ratio is the most important task of modern methodological science, the solution of which is equally necessary for both RCT and RSCS.

The methods of RCT and RSCS also have a common linguistic justification, since both foreigners and students of schools with a non-Russian language of instruction are taught speech activity in Russian. The spheres of communication of trainees depend not on the national affiliation of trainees, but on their age characteristics, future or present profession, range of interests, etc.

The classification of a number of language categories according to the level of communicative significance and situational conditionality is very promising, which is usually not differentiated either with a descriptive or functional approach to the study of linguistic phenomena. The communicative-semantic classification of linguistic phenomena is quite promising for both the RCT and the RNSH. It helps to regulate the transition from the use of ready-made, "stamped" language units by students in standard situations to self-motivated generation of speech in new conditions, spontaneously arising situations. The communicative-semantic approach to the language material helps to develop a differentiated system of exercises for the formation of skills and abilities associated with the introduction of different language facts into the speech of students.

Thus, at the present time, there is a trend towards an ever closer approximation of the RYANSH methodology with the RCT methodology. The commonality of the methodology of RCT and RSCS is based on the unity of the psychological-pedagogical, psycho-linguistic and linguistic base. Both RCT and RSCS are characterized by a clear differentiation of learning goals for different categories of trainees and the definition of different learning paths depending on the goal.

References:

- 1.Методика преподавания русского языка в национальной школе.Л.,1989.С.9.
- 2.Текучев А.В. Методика русского языка в средней школе. М.1995.С.8.
- 3.Русский язык в национальной школе: Проблемы лингводидактики. М., 1987.С.38.
- 5.Методика преподавания русского языка в национальной школе. Л.,1987.,С.11.
- 6.Рубинштейн С.Л. О мышлении и путях его исследования.М.,1968,С.15.
- 7.Калита И.В. Заметки о межкультурной коммуникации.Е.,2012.,С.45.
- 8.Калита И.В. Проблемы коммуникативной стилистики и лингвокультурологии при обучении русскому языку как иностранному. В.,2012.,С.138.